

Titanium(IV) and Zirconium(IV) Complexes of N-4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene Anthranilic Acid/*o*-Aminophenol

G. P. POKHARIYAL*

Chemistry Department, M. M. College, Khekra-201 101

Manuscript received 29 November 1982, revised 12 October 1984, accepted 3 June 1985

Complexes of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} with Schiff base ligands N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene anthranilic acid (H₂MHACAA) and N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene-*o*-aminophenol (H₂MHACAP) have been isolated and characterised on the basis of various physicochemical studies. Infrared spectral data show that the ligands act as tridentate chelating agents coordinating through phenolic oxygen, azomethine nitrogen and carboxylic oxygen.

THE preparation and characterisation of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} complexes of Schiff base ligands, N-4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetocoumarinylidene anthranilic acid/*o*-aminophenol are described in the present paper. In ligands, there are the chelated phenolic, carboxylic and azomethine groups which take part in complex formation with metal ions forming six/five membered rings.

A.R. grade sample of metal chlorides (TiCl₄ and ZrCl₄) were used. The organic solvents were of reagent quality and dried just prior to use. 4-Methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyloumarin was prepared¹ and the Schiff base ligands, H₂MHACAA and H₂MHACAP were prepared²⁻⁴ by refluxing equimolar amounts of 4-methyl-7-hydroxy-8-acetyloumarin with anthranilic acid/*o*-aminophenol in ethanol on a steam-bath for 3.5-4 h. Satisfactory elemental analyses were obtained (m.p. 155° and 161° for H₂MHACAA and H₂MHACAP, respectively).

All the complexes were prepared by the interaction of ligands with metal chlorides in 2 : 1 stoichiometric ratio in refluxing ethanol for 5-5.5 h until the evaluation of hydrogen chloride ceased. On refrigeration for a few days the reaction mixture yielded coloured crystals of complexes which were washed with water, ethanol, ether and methyl cyanide and dried in vacuum dessicator.

Titanium and zirconium were determined gravimetrically as oxide. Nitrogen was estimated by Colemann N-Analyser-29. The analytical data of the complexes are given in Table 1. The complexes are soluble in dimethylsulphoxide, dimethylformamide, bromoform, nitrobenzene and benzene. The electrical conductance values of the complexes in nitrobenzene indicate their non-electrolytic nature (0.20-0.25 Ω⁻¹ cm² mol⁻¹). The complexes of Ti^{IV} and Zr^{IV} with ligands possess magnetic moment values 0.13-0.16 B.M., indicating their diamagnetic nature.

The electronic spectra of all complexes recorded in dimethylformamide on a Cary-14 recording spectrophotometer, show a single band at 24750-24600 cm⁻¹ for titanium complexes and 24850-24360 cm⁻¹ for zirconium complexes. This may be assigned to the charge transfer band^{5,6} which is in accord with their (n-1)d⁰ ns⁰ electronic configuration.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded in the range 4000-200 cm⁻¹ on a Perkin-Elmer-577 spectrophotometer. The hydroxy (OH) group in the 7-position is very reactive due to electrometric effect⁷. The ir spectra of the ligands show characteristic absorption around 3500 (OH)⁸, 1700 (C=O) and 1625 cm⁻¹ (-(CH₂)C=N-). In complexes, the absence of ν_{OH} band, lowering of ν_{(CH₂)C=N} to 1525

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.*	Colour (Decomp. temp., °C)	Analysis % : Found/ Calcd.)		Mol. wt. Found/Calcd.)
		Ti/Zr	N	
Ti(MHACAA) ₂	Intense yellow (176-77)	6.52 (6.67)	8.73 (8.89)	701 (717.9)
Zr(MHACAA) ₂	Yellowish white (166-68)	11.88 (11.98)	8.64 (8.67)	742 (762.2)
Ti(MHACAP) ₂	Orange (193-95)	7.15 (7.28)	4.18 (4.22)	648 (661.9)
Zr(MHACAP) ₂	Yellow (184-86)	12.82 (12.98)	8.91 (8.97)	686 (705.2)

* MHACAA=C₁₅H₁₁NO₆; MHACAP=C₁₆H₁₁NO₆

cm^{-1} are noted indicating coordination of ligand through these groups ($\nu_{\text{M-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{M-N}}$ bonding⁹⁻¹⁰). The $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ bands are observed at almost the same position in the complexes, ruling out the involvement of carbonyl group in complexation. Ligand H_2MHACAA shows one band at 2950 cm^{-1} (COOH). This band disappears in the spectra of the complexes indicating the coordination of the carboxylic group¹¹ oxygen to the metal atom through deprotonation. This view is further supported by the appearance of bands^{12,13} at $400-450 \text{ (M-N)}$ and $475-525 \text{ cm}^{-1} \text{ (M-O)}$.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Dr. M. N. Sharma, Principal, M. M. College, Khekra and Dr. P. Singh, S. S. V. College, Hapur for encouragement.

References

1. A. RUSSELL and J. R. FRYE, *Org. Synth.*, 1955, 3, 281.
2. P. SINGH and G. P. POKHARIYAL, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1930, 104, 63.
3. G. P. POKHARIYAL, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1983, 60, 182.
4. R. C. SHARMA and G. P. POKHARIYAL, *Bull. Soc. Chim. Belg.*, communicated.
5. T. M. DUNN, R. S. NYHOLM and S. YAMADA, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1962, 1564.
6. P. B. DORAINI, H. H. PATTERSON and P. C. JORDAN, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1968, 49, 8845.
7. B. D. JAIN and H. B. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1968, 1, 869.
8. D. K. RASTOGI, A. K. SRIVASTAVA and B. B. AGRAWAL, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1969, 7, 732.
9. J. OSASZAR and L. KISS, *Acta Chim. Acad. Sci. Hung.*, 1973, 78, 17.
10. D. M. ADAM, "Metal-ligand and Related Vibrations", E. Arnold, London, 1967.
11. D. D. OZHA, K. N. KAUL and S. MEHTA, *Curr. Sci.*, 1975, 43, 844.
12. L. NAKAGAWA and SHRIMANONCHI, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1964, 20, 429.
13. L. SACCONI and A. SABHATINI, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1963, 25, 1989.